

The Legacy of *Rangawali Pichhaura* in Indian Traditional Textiles

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Abstract:

In the rich cultural heritage of India, textiles exhibit the regional narratives, skills of the artisans, and deep-rooted connection with the traditions. Each region celebrates its unique traditional textile: the Pashmina of Kashmir; the Phulkari of Punjab, and the Patola of Gujarat. Similarly, Rangawali Pichhaura is one of the traditional textiles of the Kumaon region of Uttarakhand, which is hand-prepared by married women. This beautiful traditional veil is gifted to the bride as a symbol of protection from evil and marital bliss. The surreal landscape of Kumaon magnifies the strokes of colorful clothing worn by the people exhibiting cultural sentiments attached to it. However, this age-old tradition is thriving to maintain its originality due to the detachment of the present generation and a lack of takers of the textile. Over the years, this region has observed an adaptation to modernization and technological advancements resulting in a drift from handmade pichhaura to being machine printed. This research aims to study the unsung legacy of Rangawali Pichhaura by investigating the historical data and documenting the narrative presented by the local families and traditional artisans of Kumaon. It further details the theories revolving around the origination of pichhaura and proposes methods to retain the originality of this traditional textile.

Keywords: Dyeing, Ornamentation, Printing, Textiles, Traditional Textiles

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1. Introduction

In the colorful mosaic of India's ethnic landscape, Uttarakhand is a melting pot of various ethnicities epitomizing a unique blend of indigenous craftsmanship and influences from the neighboring states. Each district of Uttarakhand alludes to the unique characteristics exhibited through its customs, rituals, fairs, and festivals. Most men and women of Uttarakhand can be observed wearing their traditional costumes while participating in cultural and festive occasions. Being agrarian [1], the people of Kumaon worshipped local deities dressed in beautiful clothes highlighting their culture. J.H. Batten in his official reports has mentioned that it may be observed of the hill people, that they are extremely indifferent regarding the state of their everyday apparel and continue to wear their clothes till reduced to mere shreds and tatters but on festivals, they prefer to go out in beautiful clothes or might absent themselves from festivities than appearing in tattered garments[2].

Figure 1: Kumaoni Women Source: Jaimitra Singh Bisht, 2022

Costumes are ideally an expression of the people, their culture, traditions, and the society they live in and Indian bridal wear is one such example. In northern India, it has been a tradition for the bride to wear a veil to protect her from the evil eye [3] or maybe as an act of modesty to show respect. But, not only is every part of India diverse, but even the districts of the Kumaon region of Uttarakhand are different in terms of culture and clothing. In addition, the people of Kumaon have an unmatched sentiment attached to their costumes. Kumaoni women wear a traditional veil presented at their wedding known as *pichhaura* or *rangawali pichhaura*. It becomes customary for these married women to adorn this wrap at religious ceremonies, on auspicious occasions, or while celebrating festivities [4]. It is typically 3 meters in length and 1.5 meters in width and is paired with *ghaghara* and *aangudi* or saree depending on the personal choice of the wearer.

Figure 2: Traditional Kumaoni Costume Source: Anup Sah, 2018

1.1 Traditional Kumaoni Bridal Wear

1.1.1 Aangudi/aanga/angiya - In Kumaon, an upper garment worn by the bride is commonly referred to as *aangudi*, also known as *aangda*, and *angiya* was one of the main upper garments. Traditionally, it was an adaptive version of a round neck ‘*choli*’ with a $\frac{3}{4}$ length or a full-length sleeve made of cotton, silk, or velvet. *Aangudi* is believed to have been modified to its present shape by incorporating features of the British garment ‘blouse,’ introduced by British ladies in 1816-1947 A.D. Hence, it generally had a front opening featuring snap fasteners or hook and eye or buttons as recalled by 97% of the respondents. *Aangudi* was commonly found in purple, green, red, blue, orange, and maroon. The fabric of the bride’s wear would be either silk or chenille. From the pictorial evidence, it was gathered that the bride’s *aangudi* was embellished with sequin work on the neck, cuffs, and hem or decorated with *gota-patti*.

Figure 3: Pichhaura paired with saree Source: Mrs Poonam Pant, 2023

1.1.2 *Ghaghara*- The most common traditional lower garment worn by Kumaoni women was the *ghaghara*. The *ghaghara* was like a long floor-length circular skirt. Most bridal *ghagharas* were made of 5-6 meters in chenille, silk, and cotton fabrics gathered at the waist and fuller at the hem secured at the waist with the help of a drawstring. Traditionally, women of well-off families wore red, emerald green, dark blue maroon, and purple heavily embellished *ghaghara* of chenille with *gota* and *dori* work in gold and silver.

1.1.3 *Saree*- Traditionally, silk *sarees* were worn over *aangudi*. The style of wearing a *saree* was that the *saree* was worn by tucking it from one end into the petticoat at the front and the rest of the fabric was wrapped around the waist. The wearer keeps an estimated *pallu* length over the left or right shoulder. With the remaining loosely wrapped fabric around the waist, pleats were folded and tucked in the petticoat at the front. The *palla* was then adjusted over the breasts. In Kumaon, the women wore *sarees* in two specific styles *ulta palla* (left-side drape) and *seedha palla* (right-side drape) which represented their marital status. Married women draped the *pallu* over the right shoulder and unmarried women draped it on the left.

According to Mrs Munni Mehta [5] the bridal veil was traditionally prepared by the hands of married women as a blessing. *Pichhaura* was adorned with traditional motifs hand-drawn. However, the insights shared do not match the description of what is observed presently in the cloth markets of Kumaon. The production of *rangawali pichhaura* is commercialized according to the needs of the modern market. It is designed for the masses to accept. The craft is almost on the verge of extinction. Further, there has been a lack of clarity amongst the people of Kumaon as to when and how *pichhaura* was first introduced.

1.2 Reasons for Drifting Preferences

The following are recognized as the main reasons for a change in the choice of present generations-

1.2.1 *Technological advancements*- In the internet epoch, the market is highly tapped by globalization and commercialization. The handicraft industry faces challenges due to new technology interventions and increased competition from different countries [6]. Hence, the mechanical versions at economical price points have been introduced in the market for the masses to accept.

1.2.2 *Modernization*- The present generation is upbeat with the trends. They are adaptive to ongoing styles. Therefore, the emotions attached to the traditions have blurred over a while.

1.2.3 *Challenges faced by the artisans*- The preparation of traditional *rangawali pichhaura* was occasion-specific and was prepared by the married women of the bride's family. Due to a lack of takers, presently, only a few artisans in Almora and Bageshwar practice dyeing and printing *rangawali pichhaura*. As observed by the researcher, these artisans are finding it difficult to safeguard their designs. With the cheaper versions of machine-printed *pichhaura*, it is challenging for these artisans to sustain their business.

1.3 Objectives of the study

The objectives of the present study are-

1.3.1 *To document the legacy of the Rangawali Pichhaura*

1.3.2 *To document the traditional steps involved in the preparation of Rangawali Pichhaura*

1.3.3 *To find out the factors that caused a change in the choice of the wearer from handmade pichhaura to machine-printed*

2. Material and Methods

The present paper aims to study the legacy and the traditional steps involved in preparing *rangawali pichhaura* for posterity. The research would further evaluate the methods to accomplish its overall objectives in Kumaon. The following methodology is used by the researcher while conducting the field study-

2.1 Locale of the Study

The researcher covered all the districts of the Kumaon region to carry out this study. To understand the origination of *rangawali pichhaura*, it seemed crucial to capture the sentiments of the entire region rather than studying only 2-3 districts. Hence, 5 tailors and 20 families staying together for three generations were selected from Udham Singh Nagar, Almora, Nainital, Bageshwar, Champawat, and Pithoragarh and 10 traditional artisans from Almora were interviewed leading to a sample size of 160 respondents.

2.2 Type of Research Design

2.2.1 *Exploratory research*: This type of research is undertaken to understand the narrative from the locals' point of view to substantiate the knowledge in comparison to the available secondary sources to get in-depth knowledge.

2.2.2 *Descriptive research*: This was aimed at carefully observing the Traditional Kumaoni culture and documenting the research topic.

2.3 Method of Data Collection

For primary data collection, the researcher used focused, directive, and semi-structured interviews to collect data from the respondents. The secondary data was collected from Doon Public Library; Dehradun, Almora Kitab Ghar; Almora, District Library; Nainital, and GB Pant Museum; Almora.

2.4 Sample Design

2.4.1 *Purposive Sampling Method*: For a systematic approach to the study, it was deemed important to connect with the historians of the Kumaon region and well-known artisans for which the purposive sampling method was selected.

2.4.2 *Snowball Sampling Method*: This method was selected after the existing research participants helped to identify other potential respondents who shared valuable insights in support of this study.

2.4.3 *Cluster Sampling Method*: This method was well suited to this study, as the population of each district of Kumaon was divided into smaller groups known as clusters and then the respondents were randomly selected among these clusters.

3. Results and Discussions

3.1 Legacy of the rangwali pichhaura

3.1.1 Folklore

According to ancient folklore narrated by a local priest of Rani Bagh, Haldwani, queen Jiya Rani of the Katyuri dynasty was bathing in the river. Distantly somewhere while hunting, the Mongol ruler found long hair floating in the river. Mongol ruler thought that the hair could be from a horsetail, so he ordered his soldiers to bring the horse for him. The soldiers tracked the hair and found that it was Jiya Rani who was bathing with her long hair let loose. However, the soldiers could not return without following the king's orders, which would have been considered disrespectful. The Mongol soldiers marched towards the queen and in her protection, the Katyuri soldiers covered their queen. The soldiers of Mongol and Katyur indulged in a fight and the Katyuri soldiers got killed while protecting Jiya Rani. The Mongol soldiers marched in unison to capture the queen. In a quick response to the situation, she wrapped her *ghaghara* around herself and turned into a stone. The stone was named *chitrashila*. Since then, it has been worshiped by the locals, and the place has been named after Jiya Rani as Rani Bagh in Haldwani. As *rangwali pichhaura* is meant to bring good omen and protect the bride from evil energies, some of the locals believe that maybe *chitrashila* is a representation of the *pichhaura*.

This folklore is narrated by many researchers who have worked in the field of the costumes and textiles of Kumaon. However, only 17% of respondents staying in Nainital and Almora were aware of this folklore. Still, the rest of the respondents had a different outlook on the legacy of *rangwali pichhaura*.

3.1.2 An age-old tradition introduced by the Sah community

Another plausible explanation was opined from an interview with Sub Lt (Dr.) Reetesh Sah [7]. According to Dr. Sah, 'around the late 15th century, during the Chand regime, some families migrated from the Saurashtra region and eventually settled in Kumaon. These Sah families were avid lovers of art and craft. In Kumaon, these families initiated *Rangawali Pichhaura*.' He added that whenever the Chand kings started accepting grains, oils, salt, etc., they erected a strong house called *ganj* or *thul ghar* (big house) instead of land revenue. The Shas became officers of these houses called Thulghariya Sahs. Similarly, the oldest Sahs settled in Champawat and Almora were Kummayyan Sahs. The ones who called themselves Kshatriyas were Jagati, Salimghariya, Gangola, Tola, and Kholbhiteria [8].

Figure 4: Handmade Pichhaura Source: Mrs Prabha Sah, 2023

Further corroborated by the families in Nainital, Almora, and Bageshwar, it was shared by the respondents that *pichhaura* recently has been recognized as an identifier of a Kumaoni women, whereas, it was not the case historically. Only the women of Sah families used to prepare handmade *pichhaura*, it was only after the girl of the Sah family got married to a different community that this tradition travelled to other districts of Kumaon. Prof. (Dr.) Girija Pande [9] also shed light on the topic and discussed that traditionally *pichhaura* was not observed in districts like Udham Singh Nagar and Pithoragarh but when the Kumaoni families migrated to these districts or maybe due to social media and societal influence *pichhaura* got wider acceptance.

3.2 Traditional steps of preparation of a rangwali pichhaura

Mrs Prabha Sah shared the process of dyeing *pichhaura*, according to her, ‘the raw materials available these days are completely different from what was used years ago’ [10]. The process of dyeing *pichhaura* was taught by her grandmother in 1970. Mrs. Sah also shared another interesting process from her memory in the late 19th century, the roots of Kilmora or Bhilmora were rubbed against the fabric leaving a mustard tint on the base. It is believed that *pichhaura* is a blessing of the whole universe to the woman it is presented to in her marriage.

Table 1: Tradition Tools and Raw Materials Used

S. No	Material Required	Quantity
1.	Schiffli Dupatta	1
2.	Turmeric	12-15 tola or 139-174 grams
3.	Sindoor or Vermillion	1 tola or 11.6 grams
4.	Gulenaar	4-5 tola or 46-58 grams
5.	Gud or Batasha	75 grams
6.	Copper vessel or aluminium vessel or earthen pot	1
7.	25 paisa or traditional silver coins	4-5 coins

*1 tola= 11.6 grams

Note: Traditionally term *tola* was referred to measure the quantity of raw material used. The term is still commonly used by traditional artisans while dyeing *pichhaura*.

Figure 5: Printed pichhaura using mechanical methods of printing like screen printing Source: Internet accessed on 12th June 2022

3.2. Steps involved in the traditional process were as follows;

- A plain or embroidered white cotton fabric of 3 meters in length and 1.5 meters in width was taken by the bride's mother or grandmother.
- In a copper or aluminium vessel, 139-174 grams of turmeric mixed with water was boiled and the cotton fabric was dipped in the solution for the dyeing.
- Traditionally, the dyebath was prepared in copper or aluminium vessels to brighten the dye colors.
- The fabric was left in the solution for half an hour and removed.
- The excess solution was squeezed out of the fabric.
- After achieving the base color mustard yellow, the moist fabric was spread on the ground in a shaded room for the fabric to refrain from drying.
- Simultaneously, a paste was prepared using 1 tola sindoor or vermillion, 4-5 tola gulenaar, and 7-8 tola gud or batasha added to the red dye mixture to thicken the paste.
- The printing was again carried out by the married women of the family as old silver coins during the British era or 25 paisa coins or small cotton balls used to be dipped in the paste and applied onto the dyed cotton fabric, creating small dots all over.
- The dotted patterns were achieved on each corner radiating towards the center.
- The lines were drawn by the edge of a coin, holding it vertically and continuously dipping in the paste.
- After completing the corners of rangwali pichhaura, the women worked in the middle where a four-cornered swastika was hand-drawn with the help of a coin.
- In each corner of the swastika, the sun, the moon, conch, bell, kalash devi, devta, etc., were adorned (figure 6).
- Finally, the pichhaura was dried in direct sunlight.

Figure 6: (L-R) Traditional Motifs of Surya Devta, Shankh, Ghanti, Kalash, and Chandrama

3.2.2 Traditional motifs and symbols adorned on pichhaura are as follows-

Swastika- In the middle of rangawali pichhaura, a four-cornered swastika was put. The swastika is an auspicious religious symbol of Hindu culture which is highly regarded before a new beginning. The sun, moon, shell, and kalash were adorned in each quadrant of this symbol.

Celestial Bodies - In Kumaoni culture, worshipping the celestial bodies is considered a blessing of the whole constellation. Hence, the sun, moon, and stars revered as celestial bodies were hand drawn on the rangawali

pichhaura. The stars were drawn in small dots all over, whereas in each quadrant *surya devta* (the Sun God) and *chandrama* (the Moon God) were adorned.

Shell- In one of the quadrants, the shell or conch was another auspicious symbol. In Hinduism, the conch is blown during auspicious ceremonies.

Kalash- Lastly, *kalash* was integral to religious and ceremonial occasions like weddings. It represents the universal mother goddess, fertility, good fortune, and success in life. [11]

Jali- *Jali* or *jaal* alludes to repeated patterns typically seen on the wraps draped by the women. The round motif achieved by dipping a cotton ball in *sindoor* (vermillion) representing the stars on *pichhaura* is an example of *jali*.

3.3 The Present Scenario

It is opined from the data, that 93% of respondents of the age group 18-28 years and 78% of respondents of the age group 29-39 years preferred machine-printed *pichhaura*, whereas 70% of respondents of 40 years and older preferred handmade *pichhaura*. As observed, the younger generations (18-28 years) in the Kumaon region did not have an in-depth understanding of the importance of *pichhaura*.

Figure 7: Response of different age groups on handmade and machine-printed pichhaura (n= 120)

Figure 8: Response of Kumaoni women to the tradition passed down as a legacy (n= 120)

From the above study, it is opined that 72%, 84%, 48%, and 82% of respondents from Nainital, Almora, Champawat, and Bageshwar respectively were handed down the legacy of dyeing *pichhaura* as a tradition travelled within the family since the 19th century, whereas, the respondents from Udham Singh Nagar and Pithoragarh shared that they were inspired by the society and started wearing machine printed *pichhaura* as it was not a family tradition.

Figure 9: Response on causes of change in choice of pichhaura (n= 120)

Figure 10: Water stain on pichhaura Source: Mrs Munni Mehta, Almora, 2020

Figure 10 depicts the response of women from all the districts of Kumaon to causes that led to a change in the choice of machine-printed *pichhaura* over handmade. 89% of the respondents shared that the aesthetic appeal of machine-printed *pichhaura* is better than hand-prepared ones as in traditional methods, dye fixation was not done (figure 10) may be due to inadequate knowledge. In contrast, commercially available varieties follow the standard industry procedures of dyeing and printing which are easy to maintain. The dye of handmade *pichhaura* requires attention and care, whereas, the print on machine-printed *pichhaura* is neat and clear to the viewer. 75% of the respondents did not acquire the knowledge and skills to prepare *rangawali pichhaura* and bought it from the readymade garments shop. 68% of the respondents felt that their choice changed as a cause of societal influence. 67% of the respondents shared that their sentiments attached to the age-old tradition have blurred due to migration and adaptations to geographical advancements. Watching videos on social media and regional short films influenced 58% of the respondents. Lastly, 53% of the respondents shared that they did not know how to contact the artisans who can prepare handmade *pichhaura*, as the tradition is not recognized as a commercial craft, and only a few families in Almora and Bageshwar have acquired the right skills.

4. Conclusions

The study has been able to establish the fact the age-old tradition of preparing *rangawali pichhaura* for the bride is eventually fading away. Due to the above-mentioned factors the present generation is opting for more practical solutions with easy maintenance. While conducting this research it was observed that a maximum number of people (other than respondents) had very little clarity on the origin of *pichhaura*. However, they were aware of the religious sentiments attached and the importance of this traditional wrap but it was surprising that they never tried to understand the legacy of *pichhaura*. In conclusion, it is considered crucial to hold on to the essence of this tradition and the following are the proposed methods in solution:

4.1 Takers in the Present Generation

The respondents belonging to the younger generations were enthusiastic to learn the traditional process of preparing handmade *pichhaura*. It was observed that by encouraging and recognizing the importance of *pichhaura* as a regional handicraft, respondents were willing to understand the legacy and follow the practice of dyeing and printing for their family members.

4.2 Better Dyeing Properties

Traditional printing offered poor color fastness leading the dye to leach out of the wrap. The artisans may or may not opt for the natural dyes however presently both acid and basic dyes are used. Better options are available for contemporary printing. Presently, *ladoo peela* and *gulaabi* dyes are used to achieve yellow and maroon colors respectively that offer better color fastness.

4.3 Recognition as a Regional Handicraft

In today's progressive era, artisans are facing several problems and threats caused by digitalization. In the interview, it was found that *rangawali pichhaura* is not recognized as a regional handicraft, hence the number of orders is limited to the region only. It is only possible after the state government, fashion institutions, influencers, and enthusiasts work together to promote the tradition with accurate information.

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